

AHMAD YASSAVI AND YASSAVI SECT

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Annotation: *The year of birth of Ahmad Yassavi, a great representative of mysticism, the founder of the Yassavi sect, which has a worthy place in Eastern mysticism, and one of the great representatives of Turkish poetry, is unknown.*

Key words: *Ahmad Yassavi, works, Yassavi sect*

His death is clearly stated in various written sources as 562 AH (1166-67 CE). But Nasafi also claims that Ahmad Yassavi was born in 1103 and died in 1166. According to some legends, he lived to be 130 years old. Arif Usman says, "According to the narrations, when Yassavi reached the age of 63, he entered the" chilla "by building an underground cell, and spent the rest of his life underground praying and performing rituals." According to this narration, he lived for 125 years, and according to another narration, he lived for 133 years and died in 562 AH. In general, there is very little information about Yassavi's biography, and it has not been thoroughly studied in detail and has been ignored. Ahmad Yassavi calls his homeland "Blessed Turkestan". He is orphaned very early from his parents. After the death of his father, Sheikh Ibrahim, his grandfather Arslanbobo (Arslonbob) brought him up as both a father and a teacher. Ahmad Yassavi's ancestral dynasty goes back to Muhammad Hanafi. On the advice of his grandfather, he went to Bukhara to study the lessons of Khoja Yusuf Hamadoni. Ahmad was 23 at the time. He was one of the most trusted and respected caliphs of his master. According to orientalist Arif Usman, Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani once asked Yusuf Hamadoni to tell him about the fate of his students. The teacher said, "My original caliphs were first Hodja Abdullah Barkiy, then Hodja Hasan Andoqi, then Hodja Ahmad Yassavi. Shortly after the caliphate of Hodja Ahmad Yassavi, he left for his native Turkestan. Then you will be the caliph instead." [1] As Yusuf Hamadoni said, Ahmad, who later returned to his native Yassi from Bukhara, built a madrasa and a khanaqah in the city and gathered many new students around him. Through these disciples, he began to spread the Yassaviya sect, which he founded, to Turkestan and the surrounding provinces. The students raised by Ahmad Yassavi are Mansur Bobo (Arslanbobo's son), Abul Malik Oto Tosh Khoja (Zangi Baba's father), Hakim Oto (Sulayman Boqirgani), Zangi

Oto and others. After the 12th century, two major sects of the Yassaviya sect emerged in Movarounnahr. The first is Naqshbandiya, the second is Bektashiya. There was a third sect called Ikoniya, but it did not extend beyond the Tashkent region. As in other sects of Sufism, the Yassaviya sect has its own set of rules (etiquette). These rules include the following:

1. The murid must not prefer anyone to his sheikh, he must express that absolute submission.
2. The murid must be so clever and prudent that he can perfectly understand all the rhymes and signs of his shaykh.
3. The murid must be faithful to all the aqeedahs (words) and afoolis (deeds) of the sheikh, and he must be absolutely mute and independent of them.
4. The murid must perform all the tasks of his murshid (piri) with agility and sincerity, and always please him.
5. The murid must be true to his word, true to his promise, and have no doubts in the heart of his murshid.
6. The murid must be faithful to his promise and keep his word.
7. The murid should be aware of all the secrets of his sheikh and should never think of his gesture. condition
8. For the sake of Allah, the murid must be ready to sacrifice his wealth and life in the way of his sheikh, and live as an enemy to his friend and enemy.

Ahmad (in Rasool) says that there are five domes in the human chest:

1. The heart or soul (two widths below the left breast);
2. The soul (two widths below the left breast);
3. The mystery above the heart;
4. the dome of secrecy;
5. the dome of goodness.

This means that Ahmad Yassavi captured all the domes of the spiritual world. Now his daily worries will not prevent him from communicating with the Almighty. "[2] In Ahmad Yassavi's Devoni Hikmat, which has a very deep and rich meaning, the Sufi-philosophical worldview of the thinker captures the reader's attention with his whole being. According to the sage, "knowing oneself, not the word of truth," is the key. Therefore, he says that a true Sufi is not a Sufi who seeks the pleasures of this world, but a person who prays, promotes honesty and purity, suffers from the sorrows of the world, and lives with the concerns of the people. From the beginning to the end of the work, the glorious human qualities: simplicity, humility, love, devotion, truth, justice, prudence, inseparability from man were propagated from a philosophical point of view. And conversely, evils such as ignorance, ignorance, injustice, dishonesty, and materialism are criticized. Those who possess such qualities are called to honesty and piety.

According to the scholar, a person should not live in this world believing in a wealthy statesman, this world will be left to everyone. Therefore, people should do good to each other, live with the truth in mind, and not be jealous of the wealth of others:

Beshak billig, bu dunyo barcha xalqdan o'taro,
Inonmagii molingga, bir kun qo'ldan ketaro.
Ota-ona, qarindosh keyin ketti, fikr qil,
To'rt oyoqli chubin ot bir kun senga etaro.
Dunyo uchun g'am yema, haqdin o'zgani dema,
Kishi molini yema, sirot uzra tutaro.

Until recently, Ahmad Yassavi's only work was considered to have no book other than Hikmatlar. An article by the scientist Javkon Lapasov under the headline "Nasabnoma" in the October 30, 1993 issue of the "People's Word" newspaper reported that a new work of the scientist had been discovered. The genealogy contains valuable information about the life, activities and genealogy of Ahmad Yassavi.

Thus, based on the blessed hadiths of the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) and being faithful to the path of his teachings, Hoja Ahmad Yassavi, as Mir Alisher Navoi wrote, achieved the status of the head of the "King of will and sincerity". In honor of the great poet Ahmad Yassavi, in his work "Nasayim ul-muhabbat" he said: and be a supporter of our people's future path.

USED LITERATURES:

1. 1 Orif Usmon. I drank Vahdad wine. "Muloqot" 1991, issue 6, page 52
2. 2 Nasafiy. Hoja Ahmad Yassavi. 12-13 pages.